

CLINICAL EFFICACY OF AYURVEDIC MANAGEMENT IN AMAVATA: A CASE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: *Amavata*, described in Ayurveda, is a chronic disorder caused by the interaction of *Ama* with vitiated *Vata Dosh*a, primarily affecting *Kapha*-dominant sites like joints. Its clinical features closely resemble Rheumatoid Arthritis (RA), an autoimmune condition marked by symmetrical joint pain, swelling, and stiffness. **Methods:** A 48-year-old female patient diagnosed with *Amavata* presented with *Janu Sandhishoola* (bilateral knee pain), *Sandhishotha* (swelling), *Sparshasahatwa* (tenderness), *Angamarda*, and *Aruchi*. After limited relief from allopathic therapy, she underwent Ayurvedic treatment at Premswarup swami multispeciality hospital, Kalol. The protocol included *Amapachana Vati*, *Ajmodadi Vati*, *Maharasnadi Kwath* and *Simhanada Guggulu* internally, along with *Abhyanga* using *Mahavishagarbha Taila* and *Valuka Swedana* externally. Dietary and lifestyle modifications were advised. Clinical grading and laboratory investigations (CBC,

ESR, CRP, RA test, uric acid) were used for assessment. **Results:** Significant improvement was observed: pain, swelling, and tenderness reduced. Morning stiffness and systemic symptoms subsided. Laboratory markers showed favorable trends. **Discussion:** The

integrative Ayurvedic approach, based on *Chakradatta's Chikitsa Siddhanta*, effectively managed *Amavata* through *Ama-Pachana*, *Vatahara*, and *Shothaghna* interventions. This case supports classical Ayurvedic principles in treating autoimmune joint disorders, warranting further research on larger cohorts.

KEYWORDS: After limited relief from allopathic therapy, she underwent Ayurvedic treatment at Premswarup swami multispeciality hospital, Kalol.

INTRODUCTION

Amavata is a pathological condition characterized by the accumulation of *Ama* in conjunction with vitiated *Vata Dosha*, primarily localizing in the *Sleshma Sthana* (sites dominated by Kapha).^[1], and is clinically analogous to Rheumatoid Arthritis (RA) in contemporary medicine. In the current era, sedentary lifestyles, consumption of fast and incompatible foods, and lack of physical activity contribute to *Mandagni*, which facilitates the formation of *Ama*. When this *Ama* interacts with aggravated *Vata Dosha* in *Kapha*-dominant regions, it manifests as *Amavata*, presenting with symptoms such as *Sandhi Shotha*, *Shoola*, *Sparsha Asahatva*, and *Gatra Stabdhatva*.

The clinical presentation of *Amavata* closely mirrors that of RA—a chronic, autoimmune inflammatory condition affecting both minor and major joints symmetrically^[2], particularly in the hands and feet. Epidemiological data from India indicate that RA prevalence ranges from 0.5% to 3.8% in women and 0.15% to 1.35% in men.^[3] Localization of *Ama* in joint tissues leads to hallmark features such as pain, swelling, stiffness, and tenderness.

Given the autoimmune and inflammatory nature of RA, its Ayurvedic counterpart, *Amavata*, is managed through a dual approach: *Nidana Parivarjana* (elimination of causative factors) and *Shamana* or *Shodhana Chikitsa* aimed at pacifying vitiated *Doshas*, particularly *Vata*.^[4] This integrative strategy is employed to achieve effective clinical management of *Amavata*.

METHODOLOGY

A female patient clinically diagnosed with *Amavata* was selected for the study. She was treated using a combination of *Shamana Chikitsa* as per ayurvedic protocol.

CASE PRESENTATION

A 48-year-old female patient presented with the primary complaint of...

- *Ubhya Janusandhi Shool-Shotha* and *Sparsha-Asahatwa*.

- *Angamarda*
- *Aruchi*
- Morning stiffness

HISTORY OF PRESENT ILLNESS

The patient had no significant health issues until two years ago. Since then, she has experienced persistent symptoms including *Ubhaya Janusandhi Shoola-Shotha*, *Sparsha Asahatwa*, *Angamarda*, *Aruchi* and morning stiffness. Initially, she sought allopathic treatment, which provided only temporary symptomatic relief. Subsequently, she opted for Ayurvedic management and approached the Premswarup swami multispeciality hospital, Kalol, for further evaluation and treatment.

PERSONAL HISTORY

- **Occupation:** Housewife
- **Dietary Habits:** Follows a vegetarian diet
- **Appetite:** Noted to be irregular
- **Allergies:** No known history of drug or food allergies

GENERAL EXAMINATION

- Patient's vital signs were within normal limits.
- No abnormalities were detected during systemic examination.
- The tongue (*Jihwa*) appeared coated (*Sama*), indicating possible *Ama* presence.
- All other parameters of *Ashtavidha Pariksha* were within normal range.

LOCAL EXAMINATION

- Swelling observed in both knee joints.
Left knee: Severe swelling — Grade 3
Right knee: Moderate swelling — Grade 2
- Tenderness noted in the affected joints.
- Local temperature was elevated, suggesting inflammation.
- Joint movements were restricted and painful in both knees (Flexion restricted; extension painful at terminal range).

INVESTIGATIONS DONE

- CBC

- ESR
- CRP
- RA test
- S.Uric Acid

DIAGNOSIS

The condition was diagnosed as *Amavata* (Rheumatoid Arthritis) based on classical Ayurvedic symptomatology and the diagnostic criteria established by the American Rheumatology Association (1988).^[5]

TREATMENT PLAN

Abhyantara Chikitsa

1. *Amapachana Vati*
2. *Maharasnadi Kwath*
3. *Simhanada Guggulu*
4. *Ajamodadi Vati*

Medicine	dose	Anupana	duration
<i>Amapachana Vati</i>	2 tab, twice a day before meal	<i>Koshna Jala</i>	30 days
<i>Maharasnadi Kwath</i>	25 ml, twice a day before meal	<i>Koshna Jala</i>	30 days
<i>Simhanada Guggulu</i>	500 mg, twice a day after meal	<i>Koshna Jala</i>	30 days
<i>Ajamodadi Vati</i>	2 tab, twice a day after meal	<i>Koshna Jala</i>	30 days

Bahya Chikitsa

1. *Abhyanga* with *Mahavishagarbha Taila*
2. *Valuka Swedana*

Abhyanga and *Valuka Swedana* were prescribed for a duration of 30 days as part of the Treatment protocol.

PATHYA-APATHYA ADVISED TO THE PATIENT

Aaharaja (Dietary Recommendations)

Pathya

- Grains: *Yava*, *Raktashali*, *Kulattha*
- Vegetables: *Shigru*, *Punarnava*, *Karvellak*, *Parawar*, *Ardrak*
- Pulses: Flour of *Mash*, *Rajmah*
- Condiments: *Rasona* or ginger processed with *Takra*
- Fluids: Warm water

Apathya

- Fast food, uncooked or improperly cooked items
- Excessively salty, spicy, or oily preparations
- Fish and aquatic meat
- Cold water, curd, jaggery, milk, cold beverages, ice creams
- Sweets in excess

Viharaja (Lifestyle Recommendations)***Pathya***

- Daily exposure to sunlight for at least 15 minutes
- Regular practice of *Pranayama*, yoga, and meditation

Apathya

- Sleeping during daytime
- Suppression of natural urges (*Vegavadharan*)
- Exposure to cold environments, wind, and air conditioning
- Excessive mental stress

FOLLOW-UP

A follow-up will be conducted after a period of 60 days.

ASSESSMENT CRITERIA

Grading of <i>Sandhishoola</i>	
Severity of pain	Grade
No pain	0
Mild pain	1
Moderate, but no difficulty in moving	2
Much difficulty in moving the body parts	3

Grading of <i>Sandhishotha</i>	
Severity of swelling	Grade
No swelling	0
slight swelling	1
moderate swelling	2
severe swelling	3

Grading of <i>Sparshasahatwa</i>	
Severity of tenderness	Grade
No tenderness	0
Subjective experience of tenderness	1

Wincing of face on pressure	2
Wincing of face and withdrawal of the affected part on pressure	3

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

Assessment of *Janu Sandhishoola*

Left Knee Joint		Right Knee Joint	
BT	AT	BT	AT
3	1	2	0

Assessment of *Sandhishotha*

Left Knee Joint		Right Knee Joint	
BT	AT	BT	AT
3	1	2	0

Assessment of *Sparshasahatwa*

Left Knee Joint		Right Knee Joint	
BT	AT	BT	AT
3	0	3	0

INVESTIGATIONS

Investigation	BT	AT
Hb%	10.1	12.6
Neutrophils	68%	64%
Lymphocytes	29%	32%
Monocytes	02%	03%
Eosinophils	01%	01%
Total Platelet Count	263000	251000
ESR	48 mm/hr	18 mm/hr
RA Test	35.5 IU/mL	16 IU/mL
CRP	21.40 mg/L	4.80 mg/L
Uric acid	6.2 mg/dL	3.2 mg/dL
RBS	94 mg/dl	102 mg/dl

**REPORTS
BEFORE**

PREMSWARUP SWAMI MULTISPECIALITY HOSPITAL
A Teaching Hospital of Swaminarayan Institute
of Medical Science & Research
(Managed by Shree Swaminarayan Vishvamangal Gurukul)

Adrees: Ahmedabad-Mehsana Highway, At&Po.-Saij, Ta.-Kalol, Dist.-Gandhinagar,
 Gujarat-382725, Contact: +91-8866213131, Website:www.psmhospital.org

TEST REPORT

Name	Mrs.Bharti Patel	Reg. No	021246/0169
Age/Sex	48 Years / Female	Reg. Date	03-Apr-2025 10:10 AM
Ref. By	Dr. Vishal Solanki	Collected On	03-Apr-2025 10:15 AM
Client Name		Report Date	03-Apr-2025 03:20 PM

Parameter	Result	Unit	Biological Ref. Interval
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COMPLETE BLOOD COUNT (CBC)
 Specimen: EDTA blood

HB & RBC INDICES

Hemoglobin (SLS method)	10.1	g/dL	12.5 - 16.0
RBC Count (Electrical Impedance)	4.80	million/cmm	4.2 - 5.4
Hematocrit (Electrical Impedance)	45.20	%	37 - 47
MCV (Calculated)	83.22	fL	78 - 100
MCH (Calculated)	30.0	Pg	27 - 31
MCHC (Calculated)	31.86	%	30 - 35
RDW (Calculated)	14.40	%	11.5 - 14.0
PDW	16.4	%	10 - 17.9
MPV	7.8	fL	7.4 - 10.4
WBC Count (Flowcytometry)	8200	/cmm	4000 - 10500

DIFFERENTIAL COUNT (Manual By Microscopy)

Neutrophils (%)	68	%	42 - 75
Lymphocytes (%)	29	%	20 - 70
Eosinophils (%)	01	%	1 - 4
Monocytes (%)	02	%	2 - 8
Basophils (%)	00	%	0 - 2

PLATELET COUNT

Platelet Count	263000	/cmm	150000 - 450000
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ERYTHROCYTE SEDIMENTATION RATE

ESR (After 1 hour)	48	mm/hr	ESR AT 30 Min : 3-12 ESR AT 30 Min : 13-20
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BLOOD GROUPING & Rh TYPING

Blood Group	: " B "
Rh Factor	: " POSITIVE "

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SERUM URIC ACID

TEST	RESULT	UNIT	REFERENCE INTERVAL
S. URIC ACID	6.2	mg/dL	3.4 to 7.0 mg/dL

Interpretation:

Serum uric acid levels are very labile and show day to day and seasonal variation in some people. Levels are also increased by emotional stress, total fasting and increased body weight. Serum uric acid levels are used to diagnose and monitor treatment of gout, monitor chemotherapeutic treatment of neoplasms to avoid renal urate deposition with possible renal failure.

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RHEUMATOID FACTOR, RA

INVESTIGATION	RESULT	UNIT	REFERENCE INTERVAL
RHEUMATOID FACTOR, RA, SERUM Immunoturbidimetry	: 35.5	IU/mL	0-18.00 IU/mL

Physiologic Basis:

Rheumatoid factor (RF) consists of heterogeneous autoantibodies, usually of the IgM class, that react against the Fc region of human IgG. Most methods detect only IgM-class RF.

Interpretation:

Positive in: Rheumatoid arthritis (75-90%), Sjögren syndrome (80-90%), scleroderma, dermatomyositis, SLE (30%), sarcoidosis, Waldenstrom macroglobulinemia, chronic infection.

Drugs: methyldopa, others.

Low-titers of RF (eg. $\leq 1:80$) are questionable and can be found in healthy older patients (20%), in 1-4% of normal individuals, and in a variety of acute immune responses (eg, viral infections, including infectious mononucleosis and viral hepatitis), chronic bacterial infections (tuberculosis, leprosy, subacute infective endocarditis), and chronic active hepatitis.

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COAGULATION PROFILE

TEST	RESULT	UNIT	REFERENCE INTERVAL
Bleeding Time	: 02:40	MINS	Up to 5 Mins.
Clotting Time	: 05:25	MINS	Up to 11 Mins.

BIOCHEMISTRY ANALYSIS

Random Blood Glucose (RBS)	: 94.00	mg/dl	60 - 130 mg/dl
C.R.P. Test (C Reactive Protein)	: 21.40	mg/L	0.0 – 5.0 mg/dl

Interpretation:

1. Measurement of CRP is useful for the detection and evaluation of infection, tissue injury, inflammatory disorders, and associated diseases.
2. High sensitivity CRP (hsCRP) measurements may be used as an independent risk marker for the identification of individuals at risk for future cardiovascular disease.
3. Increase in CRP values are non-Specific and should not be interpreted without a complete history.

AFTER

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TEST REPORT

Name	Mrs. Bharti Patel	Reg. No	021246/0169
Age/Sex	48 Years / Female	Reg. Date	04-July-2025 09:30 AM
Ref. By	Dr. Vishal Solanki	Collected On	04-July-2025 09:35 AM
Client Name		Report Date	04-July-2025 02:40 PM

Parameter	Result	Unit	Biological Ref. Interval
COMPLETE BLOOD COUNT (CBC)			
Specimen: EDTA blood			
HB & RBC INDICES			
Hemoglobin (SLS method)	12.6	g/dL	12.5 - 16.0
RBC Count (Electrical Impedance)	4.60	million/cmm	4.2 - 5.4
Hematocrit (Electrical Impedance)	44.60	%	37 - 47
MCV (Calculated)	86.35	fL	78 - 100
MCH (Calculated)	29.20	Pg	27 - 31
MCHC (Calculated)	32.60	%	30 - 35
RDW (Calculated)	13.20	%	11.5 - 14.0
PDW	14.2	%	10 - 17.9
MPV	7.6	fL	7.4 - 10.4
WBC Count (Flowcytometry)	7400	/cmm	4000 - 10500
DIFFERENTIAL COUNT (Manual By Microscopy)			
Neutrophils (%)	64	%	42 - 75
Lymphocytes (%)	32	%	20 - 70
Eosinophils (%)	01	%	1 - 4
Monocytes (%)	03	%	2 - 8
Basophils (%)	00	%	0 - 2
PLATELET COUNT			
Platelet Count	251000	/cmm	150000 - 450000
ERYTHROCYTE SEDIMENTATION RATE			
ESR (After 1 hour)	18	mm/hr	ESR AT 30 Min : 3-12 ESR AT 30 Min : 13-20
BLOOD GROUPING & Rh TYPING			
Blood Group	: " B "		
Rh Factor	: " POSITIVE "		

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COAGULATION PROFILE

TEST	RESULT	UNIT	REFERENCE INTERVAL
Bleeding Time	: 02:45	MINS	Up to 5 Mins.
Clotting Time	: 05:20	MINS	Up to 11 Mins.

BIOCHEMISTRY ANALYSIS

Random Blood Glucose (RBS)	: 102.00	mg/dl	60 - 130 mg/dl
C.R.P. Test (C Reactive Protein)	: 4.80	mg/L	0.0 – 5.0 mg/dl

Interpretation:

1. Measurement of CRP is useful for the detection and evaluation of infection, tissue injury, inflammatory disorders, and associated diseases.
2. High sensitivity CRP (hsCRP) measurements may be used as an independent risk marker for the identification of individuals at risk for future cardiovascular disease.
3. Increase in CRP values are non-Specific and should not be interpreted without a complete history.

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RHEUMATOID FACTOR, RA

INVESTIGATION	RESULT	UNIT	REFERENCE INTERVAL
RHEUMATOID FACTOR, RA, SERUM <small>Immunoturbidimetry</small>	: 16	IU/mL	0-18.00 IU/mL

Physiologic Basis:

Rheumatoid factor (RF) consists of heterogeneous autoantibodies, usually of the IgM class, that react against the Fc region of human IgG. Most methods detect only IgM-class RF.

Interpretation:

Positive in: Rheumatoid arthritis (75-90%), Sjögren syndrome (80-90%), scleroderma, dermatomyositis, SLE (30%), sarcoidosis, Waldenström macroglobulinemia, chronic infection.

Drugs: methyldopa, others.

Low-titers of RF (eg, $\leq 1:80$) are questionable and can be found in healthy older patients (20%), in 1-4% of normal individuals, and in a variety of acute immune responses (eg, viral infections, including infectious mononucleosis and viral hepatitis), chronic bacterial infections (tuberculosis, leprosy, subacute infective endocarditis), and chronic active hepatitis.

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Client Name		Report Date	04-July-2025 02:40 PM

SERUM URIC ACID

TEST	RESULT	UNIT	REFERENCE INTERVAL
S. URIC ACID	3.2	mg/dL	3.4 to 7.0 mg/dL

Interpretation:

Serum uric acid levels are very labile and show day to day and seasonal variation in some people. Levels are also increased by emotional stress, total fasting and increased body weight. Serum uric acid levels are used to diagnose and monitor treatment of gout, monitor chemotherapeutic treatment of neoplasms to avoid renal urate deposition with possible renal failure.

DISCUSSION

Chakradatta was the first to outline the therapeutic principles for *Amavata*, recommending *Langhana*, *Swedana*, drugs with *Tikta* and *Katu Rasa*, *Deepana*, *Virechana*, *Snehapana*, *Anuvasana Basti*, and *Kshara Basti*, while *Yogaratanakara* later added *Upanaha* without *Sneha*. *Amavata* arises from the vitiation of *Vata Dosha* and the accumulation of *Ama* due to *Mandagni*, with *Langhana*—especially in the form of *Laghu Ahara*—considered the primary intervention.^[6] As an *Amasayotha Vyadhi* and *Rasaja Vikara*, *Amavata* responds well to *Langhana* and *Swedana*, particularly *Ruksha Sweda* like *Valuka Pottali*, which alleviates stiffness and pain by pacifying *Vata*.^[7] *Simhanada Guggulu*^[8] (500 mg twice daily) and *Maharasnadi Kwatha* (20 ml twice daily with lukewarm water) were administered; the former possesses *Laghu*, *Ruksha*, *Ushna*, and *Tikshna* qualities and offers *Shothaghna*, *Shoolaghna*, *Jwaraghna*, *Balya*, and *Amavatahara* effects, while *Ajamodadi Vati* and *Amapachana Vati* offers *Deepana*, *Ama-Pachana*, enhancing *Agni Bala* and disrupting the pathogenesis (*Samprapti*) of *Amavata*. *Maharasnadi Kwatha* complements this with *Shothahara* and *Shoolaghna* properties.^[9] Additionally, *Mahavishgarbha Taila* comprising *Dhatura*, *Vatsanabha*, *Eranda*, and other *Vatahara* herbs, was applied locally for its *Vedanasthapana*, *Shothahara*, *Swedajanana*, *Deepana*, and *Pachana* actions, promoting *Vatashamana* and local *Ama-Pachana*.^[10] Clinical assessments before and after treatment

showed marked improvement in both subjective symptoms and objective criteria, validating the efficacy of this integrative Ayurvedic approach.

CONCLUSION

This case study suggests that *Amavata* can be managed effectively and safely using the *Chikitsa Siddhanta* outlined by *Acharya Chakradatta*. However, as this is based on a single case, further research involving a larger patient population is necessary to validate its therapeutic efficacy.

REFERENCES

1. Tripathi Ravidatta, Charaka samhita with Vidyamanorama Hindi Chaukhamba commentary, Sanskrit Pratishthan, Delhi, 2009.
2. Boon NA, Colledge NR, Walker BR, Hunter JA. Musculoskeletal disorders. Davidson's Principles and Practice of Medicine. 20th ed., Ch. 25. Edinburgh: Churchill Livingstone-Elsevier, 2006; 1101-4.
3. Prevalence of Rheumatoid arthritis <https://www.researchgate.net>>, 1488.
4. Chaturvedi G, Shastri K, editors. Charaka Samhita of Agnivesha, Siddhi Sthana, Ch. 2, Ver. 13. Reprint ed. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Bharati Academy, 2007; 981.
5. Arnett FC et al. The American Rheumatism Association 1987 revised criteria for the classification of rheumatoid arthritis. Arthritis & Rheumatism Arthritis & Rheumatism-Arthritis Care & Research, 1988; 31(3): 315-324).
6. Tripathi Ravidatta, Charaka samhita with Vidyamanorama Hindi Chaukhamba commentary, Sanskrit Pratishthan, Delhi, 2009; Su 23/25 (Pg.319).
7. Tripathi Ravidatta, Charaka samhita with Vidyamanorama Hindi Chaukhamba commentary, Sanskrit Pratishthan, Delhi, 2009; Su 22/11 (Pg.309)
8. Das Govinda, Bhaishajya Ratnavali, Hindi commentary by Ambikadatta Shastri, Chaukhambha Prakashana, Varanasi, Edition 2014, Amavata chikitsa, 29/181-189, (Pg no.628)
9. Murthy K.R., Shrikantha, Chaukhambha Prakashan, by Sharngadhara, Sharangdhara Samhita Madhyamakhandha 2/89 – 95. Page 66-68.
10. Das Govinda, Bhaishajya Ratnavali Volume -II, English commentary by Kaajiv alaochan, Choukhambha Sanskrit Bhavan Varanasi, chapter 26, 2005; shloka no.593-606; 233.